

LEARNING RETENTION ON COLREGS AMONG MARITIME TRANSPORTATION GRADUATES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to quantify and interpret the learning retention of collision regulations (COLREGS) among maritime transportation graduates. Utilizing a sequential-explanatory mixed method research design, this study investigated the knowledge retention of maritime transportation graduates with regards to COLREGS as well as the contributing factors which led to the results. A standardized assessment tool was procured from the Academe Assessment Center and assessed 50 participants which were identified via the snowball sampling method within the university training center. Findings revealed an average score of 37.12% and a “Very Poor” learning retention as merely 6 out of 50 participants passed. Additionally, the study identified the weakest retention regarding appropriate sounds signals, exemptions, and audit scheme rules in COLREGS. Themes generated helped identify the contributing factors leading to high and low scores such as the specific variation of sound signals, compulsory review of exemptions and audit schemes, and efficacy of simulator and hands-on learning. Ultimately, the researchers identified that the main contributing factors of the results were due to participants’ personality traits, surroundings, and situations. Based on these results, proposing refresher courses and modules in various mediums would greatly benefit the retention rate of seafarers and consolidate knowledge on COLREGS.

Keywords: *Learning Retention, COLREGS, Contributing Factors, Personality Traits, Maritime Transportation Graduates*

INTRODUCTION

COLREGS knowledge is pivotal for maritime safety and the competence of seafarers. However, there needs to be more understanding of how effectively graduates retain and apply this knowledge in real-world onboard situations. This gap in knowledge retention posed significant challenges to the maritime industry and academic institutions, which strive to produce competent and knowledgeable professionals. The main issue of this study addressed more than the academic curriculum as it also affects maritime operations safety and efficacy.

The work of Del Rosario et al. (2020) on enhancing the governance of maritime higher education highlights the significance of governance in guaranteeing the efficacy of maritime education, encompassing the impairment of COLREGS knowledge. The International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea, or COLREGS, controls the manner in which the vessels should act in different situations in order to prevent collisions at sea. By training qualified mariners, utilizing effective retention strategies can help leaders in the seafaring industry meet the retention objectives of their educational institutions and develop a positive and healthy work environment (Cockcroft & Lameijer, 2003).

Seafarers were able to enhance their job skills, which played a role in promotions and career development, by demonstrating a solid comprehension of COLREGS. A high retention rate for COLREGS can also greatly increase operational maritime safety. Thus, acquiring this knowledge is crucial for maritime transportation graduates since it directly impacts their capacity to navigate ships safely and comply with international maritime regulations. Indeed, implementing effective retention strategies can assist in developing stronger and lasting standards, which will allow the integration of retention strategies that increase worker satisfaction and improve mariners' training on waterways.

This research was conducted at UC-METC (University of Cebu - Maritime Education and Training Center), a renowned maritime education institution in Cebu, Philippines due to its pivotal role in training and educating future seafarers in the Philippines. The school's reputation and expertise in maritime education served as an ideal location to investigate the learning retention of COLREGS studies among BSMT (Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation) graduates. For an in-depth analysis, this study also aimed to understand and assess the reasons behind the data gathered. With the aid of a brief interview with the participants of this study, the researchers aimed to delve into the factors contributing to the participants' learning retention outcomes based on the results of the data collection process. As the study revealed a very poor learning retention level among the participants, the objective was to understand the contributing factors which led to these results.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this study quantified and interpreted the learning retention of COLEGS among maritime transportation graduates in the University of Cebu - Maritime Education and Training Center from academic years 2020-2023.

Specifically, the study investigated the following questions:

1. What is the level of learning retention on COLREGS among the participants?
2. What were the contributing factors leading to high and low scores of participants of the COLREGS Assessment?
3. What sound recommendations were proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a sequential-explanatory mixed method research design which emphasized a two-phase style gathering both quantitative and qualitative data, respectively. The researchers first used a standardized assessment tool validated from the Academe Assessment Center (AAC) to test the participant's knowledge retained regarding collision regulations. Subsequently, the researchers contacted and asked follow-up queries with regards to multiple participants' performance with the standardized assessment tool. For an efficient data gathering process, the researchers utilized the snow-ball sampling method in identifying the appropriate participants for the study at the University of Cebu - METC campus training center. The participants of this study were all fully informed of their rights. As there were no incentives in participating in this endeavor, all participants were briefed that participation was purely voluntary, subsequently of their right to withdraw, and that all data was strictly confidential. The researchers lastly employed a simple percentage data treatment calculation and a thematic analysis in analyzing the data collected.

RESULTS

Table 1
Score and Percentages of the Participants

Participant	Score	Percentage	Participant	Score	Percentage
No. 1	21	42 %	No. 26	15	30 %
No. 2	17	34 %	No. 27	14	28 %
No. 3	15	30 %	No. 28	17	34 %
No. 4	24	48 %	No. 29	15	30 %

No. 5	18	36 %	No. 30	21	42 %
No. 6	26	52 %	No. 31	18	36 %
No. 7	14	28 %	No. 32	10	20 %
No. 8	16	32 %	No. 33	14	28 %
No. 9	15	30 %	No. 34	8	16 %
No. 10	18	36 %	No. 35	23	46 %
No. 11	21	42 %	No. 36	20	40 %
No. 12	16	32 %	No. 37	13	36 %
No. 13	15	30 %	No. 38	37	74 %
No. 14	29	58 %	No. 39	21	42 %
No. 15	21	42 %	No. 40	22	44 %
No. 16	14	28 %	No. 41	21	42 %
No. 17	20	40 %	No. 42	21	42 %
No. 18	11	22 %	No. 43	13	26 %
No. 19	30	60 %	No. 44	15	30 %
No. 20	25	50 %	No. 45	21	42 %
No. 21	30	60 %	No. 46	18	36 %
No. 22	17	34 %	No. 47	17	34 %
No. 23	11	22 %	No. 48	24	48 %
No. 24	17	34 %	No. 49	15	30 %
No. 25	17	34 %	No. 50	17	34 %

Table 2
Item Analysis

Difficulty	DISCRIMINATION						Total	INTERPRETATION
	<.00	.00-.14	.15-.24	.25-.29	.30-.44	≥.45		
81-100%					13		1	Very Easy
61-80%				50	1, 22		3	Easy (Good Items)

41-60%		3,10,21, 34, 42,48	4,7,47	28,29	8, 12	24	14	Average (Best Items)
21-40%	43	32,37, 45	17,18, 25,31, 49	6,16,23,27, 30,38,39, 41,44, 46	5, 14, 20,33, 36	2, 15	26	Difficult (Good Items)
0-20%	11, 40	9,19,35	26				6	Very Difficult
Total	3	12	9	13	10	3	50	
	Reject		Needs Revision		Acceptable			

Table 3
Audit Trail on the Reasons for the Level of Difficulty

Code Name	Significant Statement	Formulated Meanings	Themes	Clustered/ Major Themes
RJM	<i>nag lisod mi sa sound signals kay daghan lain lain specific signals para sa specific situations like aground, overtaking, altering course, etc.</i>	The participant stated that there are different sound signals for specific situations.	Theme 1 - Maritime graduate students found learning sound signals difficult because there are different sound signals for different scenarios.	Specific Variation of Sound Signals
	<i>tas sa rule 38 ug sa audit scheme medyu naka limot nami ana.</i>	The participant stated that they have forgotten the lessons regarding Rule 38 and Audit Schemes	Theme 2- Maritime graduate students tend to forget topics on Exemptions and Audit Schemes because of lack of review.	Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes
RES	<i>sa sound signals sir medyu nag lisud ko ana kay sa una na topic kay wala gyud naka experience sa simulator kay mainly theory lang tas basa2 lang mi, maong mag lisud ko ana</i>	The participant stated that learning COLREGS would have been easier with the aid of the simulator as their experience with the subject was mainly theory.	Theme 3 - Maritime graduate students found remembering sound signals difficult due to lack of simulator and hands-on experience.	Efficacy of Simulator and Hands-on Learning
	<i>Tapus sa rule 38 exemptions and audit scheme kay kana wala jud ko naka remember na, naay laboratory or simulator pero rarely lang</i>	The participant stated that they do not remember the exemptions and audit scheme topics.	Theme 2- Maritime graduate students tend to forget topics on Exemptions and Audit Schemes because of lack of review.	Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes
BRJ	<i>para nako dong kay nag lisud ko answer ato sa mga questions kay wala ko naka study, pero ang kanang sound signals usa na sya sa mga lisud sad na topic in colregs kay daghan classifications gud</i>	The participant stated that they were not able to review the different sound signals as it was one of the difficult topics in colregs as it has many different classifications.	Theme 1 - Maritime graduate students found learning sound signals difficult because there are different sound signals for different scenarios.	Specific Variation of Sound Signals

	<i>Ang rule 38 exemptions ug audit scheme kay naka limot na guro ko ana and wala ko naka study maong wala guro ko naka answer ana na mga topics sa survey ninyo</i>	The participant stated that they have forgotten regarding exemptions and audit schemes and they were not able to review these topics.	Theme 2- Maritime graduate students tend to forget topics on Exemptions and Audit Schemes because of lack of review.	Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes
MIMI	<i>ang sa sound signals sir kay nag lisud ko ana kay saamo na time rarely lang mag laboratory about ana puro lang kami basa2 ng lisud ko dum-dum ato na topic</i>	The participant stated that they found learning sound signals difficult because during their time they were only able to use the laboratory/simulators on rare occasions as they were only reading about the topics.	Theme 3 - Maritime graduate students found remembering sound signals difficult due to lack of simulator and hands-on experience.	Efficacy of Simulator and Hands-on Learning
	<i>tapus sa rule 38 and kana audit scheme kay wala ko ana naka study gud mao guro wala ko naka answer</i>	The participant stated that they were not able to study regarding exemptions and audit schemes as much.	Theme 2- Maritime graduate students tend to forget topics on Exemptions and Audit Schemes because of lack of review.	Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes
KYD	<i>aguy daghan diay na mali sa sound signals haha pati ako nag lisud sad kay daghan mana sila gud klase-klase na sound signals naay uban same-same lang maong dapat kailangan maminaw</i>	The participant stated that even they found it [studying sound signals] difficult because there are different sound signals and some are even similar to one another.	Theme 1 - Maritime graduate students found learning sound signals difficult because there are different sound signals for different scenarios.	Specific Variation of Sound Signals
	<i>tas ang sa rule 38 exemptions tas audit scheme kay naka limot ko ato while nag take sa survey ninyo kay wala ko naka review</i>	The participant stated that they had forgotten the rules in exemptions and audit schemes when they took the survey.	Theme 2- Maritime graduate students tend to forget topics on Exemptions and Audit Schemes because of lack of review.	Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes
DEBI	<i>ay sir wala man gud ko ana naka study sa mga topics pag exam gud mao guro wala ko naka answer, pero sa sound signals kay medyo nag lisod ko kay daghan mangod na klase-klase na mga signals</i>	The participant stated that they found answering the sound signals questions difficult because there are a lot of different signals.	Theme 1 - Maritime graduate students found learning sound	Specific Variation of Sound Signals
	<i>tapus ang rule 38 ug kanang audit scheme kay wala ko naka remember sa kana na mga rules pag answer nako gud naka limot na guro</i>	The participant stated that they forgot about the exemptions and audit schemes.	Theme 2- Maritime graduate students tend to forget topics on Exemptions and Audit Schemes because of lack of review.	Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes

Table 4
Mean and Modal Scores and Percentages of the Participants

Measure of Central Tendency	Score (out of 50)	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
Mean	18.56	37.12	Very Poor
Mode	21	42	Very Poor

Table 5
Highest and Lowest Performing Participants

Rank	Participant No.	Score	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
1	# 38	37 / 50	74	Good
2	# 19	30 / 50	60	Poor
3	# 21	30 / 50	60	Poor
48	# 23	11 / 50	22	Very Poor
49	# 32	10 / 50	20	Very Poor
50	# 34	8 / 50	16	Very Poor

Table 6
Qualifying Maritime Transportation Graduates

Rank	Participant No.	Score	Percentage	Interpretation
1	# 38	37 / 50	74	Good
2	# 19	30 / 50	60	Poor
3	# 21	30 / 50	60	Poor
4	# 14	29 / 50	58	Poor
5	# 6	26 / 50	52	Poor
6	# 20	25 / 50	50	Poor

DISCUSSION

Table 1 showed the scores in the second column and the percentages in the third column based on each participant's performance upon answering the standardized assessment tool. As seen in Table 1, which were boldfaced, only 6 among the 50 participants performed equal to or above the passing criteria of 50%. The participants were given a 50% standard passing goal of whether actual learning retention regarding COLREGS was observed.

Table 2 presented the results of the item analysis procured from the Academe Assessment Center (AAC) based on the answers among this research's fifty (50) participants. It showed the items of the standardized questionnaire, which were sub categorized as very easy, easy, average, difficult, and very difficult.

Upon completion of the item analysis, only one item was considered "very easy" and this was item number 13. The question at hand talked about the color of the distress signal by a rocket or hand flare with a discrimination value of 0.30-0.44, indicating an acceptable question. Under the COLREGS table of specifications procured from the Academe Assessment Center, this item was under the application cognitive domain. All this information implied that maritime graduates retained sufficient information regarding the application of the appropriate color of the flare at times of distress, which was a red-colored light. Seafarers and maritime graduates knew so much about the color of the distress flare signal because it is a critical aspect of marine safety and survival. Pyrotechnics onboard, such as distress flare signals, are vital in catching the attention of vessels or aircraft within the vicinity for requesting assistance during emergencies (Bhattacharjee, 2019). Another noteworthy implication was that maritime graduates could correctly identify the appropriate color for the distress signal through the numerous films featuring distress signals. Films concerned with emergencies tend to showcase a specific colored distress signal to catch the attention of passing vessels. Hence, it was implied that through the subconscious viewing of films, whether based on real-life events or pure science fiction, one can acquire basic knowledge to transform one's life and relate this to real-life applications (Frederic & Brussat, 2018).

Three (3) items were considered as "easy", namely items 1, 22, and 50. These items were considered "good items," as seen in Table 2, with discrimination values of 0.25-0.29 and 0.30-0.44, respectively, indicating that these were acceptable items within the standardized assessment tool. Although item number 50 was under a discrimination value considered "needs revision", upon a brief discussion with the Academe Assessment Center (AAC), they still considered items in this discrimination value acceptable. Items 1, 22, and 50 assessed the knowledge retained for sound signals under the application, remembering, and application cognitive domains, respectively, as seen in the table of specifications for COLREGS. This implied that maritime graduates considered these questions regarding the sound signals easy questions based on their knowledge retained. Although this information is fundamentally mandatory for a seafarer to be knowledgeable about, it also plays a crucial role in maritime safety, especially during restricted visibility conditions. It conveys a vessel's intention and current situation, significantly when

adverse weather restricts the visual aspect of navigation. Seafarers and maritime graduates are well-versed in the application of appropriate sound signals, as communicating effectively and preventing collisions are a top priority (Aarthi & Krithika, 2022). It was implied that most maritime graduates are knowledgeable about sound signals due to the nature of the course's requirement for simulation training and exercises. Advanced simulators highly impact seafarers in terms of honing their skills and experiences with navigating using onboard equipment. They could develop the necessary skills safely and effectively without the immediate danger compared to doing so onboard ships. A maritime student must develop their experiences in terms of navigating. Doing so with the aid of simulators is an effective method for retaining knowledge learned (Sangeetha & Gomathy, 2019).

Moving forward, the items considered "very good" items under the average category, to name a few items, were items number 8, 12, and 29. Like those under the easy category, these items assessed the participant's knowledge of appropriate sound signals with discrimination values of 0.25-0.29 and 0.30-0.44 about acceptable questions, as stated in the abovementioned paragraph. These questions belonged more to the application cognitive domain. This implied that maritime schools emphasized how to effectively memorize and apply specific sound signals and durations of blasts to identify the appropriate interpretation of signals for effective collision avoidance (Aarthi & Krithika, 2022). As COLREGS is a purely theoretical course, it was implied that there was a gap between the curriculum-theoretical aspect and the application aspect. Situations in real scenarios are continuously dynamic due to the changing demands at sea. Different vessels have different requirements, as not all information is constant. It was up to the individual to apply the knowledge gained to the problem given certain circumstances. Problem-based learning is an inherent problem when it comes to training the new generation of seafarers. As technology advances, the need to adapt the curriculum is fairly evident, and the application of knowledge gained based on dynamic situations needs to be practiced better (Costley, 2014).

As for the "difficult" items, which comprised most of the items in the standardized test questionnaire, as seen in Table 2, items 2 and 15 were considered good items, to name a few. These items were deemed acceptable with discrimination values of greater or equal to 0.45. These items assessed the participant's knowledge regarding the auditing portion of COLREGS, which was unrelated to the navigation aspect but more to the regulation compliance of COLREGS. Questions such as these were under the remembering and understanding cognitive domain under the COLREGS table of specifications, which did not require analysis and the application of knowledge to be retained. This implied that seafarers or maritime graduates often overlooked the last parts of COLREGS due to the complex nature of these rules in understanding its specifications. Due to the intricacies of auditing, it is often overlooked as it requires a deeper level of understanding of different regulations, conventions, and codes. As auditing is required to monitor and enforce compliance with necessary regulations, basic surface knowledge regarding the audit schemes in COLREGS requires more profound levels of understanding and experience (Batalden & Sydnese, 2013).

Lastly, some items under the "very difficult" category consisted of questions regarding rule 38 of COLREGS, such as items 19 and 35. With discrimination values of 0.0-0.14, these items were considered under the need's revision discrimination interpretation and the understanding and analysis of cognitive domains, respectively. These items assessed the appropriate number of years of validity regarding the exemptions stipulated in annexes of COLREGS as well as concerning appropriate exemptions in specific rules. Similar to the abovementioned paragraph, it is worth noting the implication of how much the last parts of COLREGS were being overlooked. Rules such as these are difficult to understand as they require a higher level of understanding regarding the rules and their specifications. Maritime graduates find it challenging to identify the appropriate exemptions in COLREGS as they are less frequently encountered than other rules under COLREGS. Due to the specific and complex nature of this rule, it is less frequently encountered than the navigational rules of COLREGS (Porathe, 2019).

Table 3 presented the audit trail and the reasons for the difficulty level of the questions presented in the standardized assessment tool. It showcased the participants' responses upon a brief interview after the researchers found the common topics regarding the difficult items: sound signals, rule 38 exemptions, and audit schemes. The table above presented the formulated meanings from the significant statements of the participants, after which themes were created and a clustered or central theme was formulated.

Theme Cluster 1: Specific Variation of Sound Signals

The Specific Variation of Sound Signals in COLREGS refers to the unique patterns and characteristics of sound signals used in the Convention on the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREGS). In the context of maritime regulations, sound signals play a crucial role in indicating the intentions and actions of vessels to avoid collisions and ensure safe navigation. The COLREGS specify distinct sound signals that vessels must use in various situations to communicate effectively with other vessels. These signals include short and prolonged blasts on the ship's whistle or horn, each with specific meanings and indications (Marine et al., 2022). For example, one short blast indicates an intention to overtake, while two short blasts signal a course change to starboard. Understanding and correctly interpreting these specific variations of sound signals outlined in the COLREGS is essential for mariners to navigate safely and adhere to international maritime regulations, ultimately ensuring the safety of vessels at sea (Boat U.S. Foundation, 2016).

The participants were interviewed regarding the reason behind difficulties and their answers in the standardized assessments tool. Below are a few of their responses:

"Nag lisod mi sa sound signals kay daghan lain lain specific signals para sa specific situations like aground, overtaking, altering course, etc." (*We had a difficult time with sound signals because they have different specific signals for specific situations like aground, overtaking, altering course, etc.*). -RJM-

“Para nako dong kay nag lisod ko answer ato sa mga questions kay wala ko naka study, pero kanang sound signals usa na sya sa mga lisud sad na topic in colregs kay daghan classifications gd”. (*For me, I had a difficult time answering the questions because I was not able to study, but the topic of sound signals is one of the difficult topics in colregs because it has many classifications*). -BRJ-

“Aguy daghan diay na mali sa sound signals haha pati ako nag lisud sad kay daghan mana sila gud klase-klase na sound signals naay uban same-same lang maong dapat kailangan maminaw”. (*Oh no it seems there are many who got the sound signals wrong, even I find it difficult because there are many different kinds of sound signals and some are even similar which is why we should listen carefully*). -KYD-

“Ay sir wala man gud ko ana naka study sa mga topics pag exam gud mao guro wala ko naka answer, pero sa sound signals kay medyo nag lisod ko kay daghan mangod na klase-klase na mga signals” (*Sir I was not able to study these topics when taking the exam which was why I could not answer, but I found the sound signals topic somewhat difficult because there are many different signals*). -DEBI-

Theme Cluster 2: Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes

The maritime industry has several audit schemes to ensure safety regulations and standards compliance. One such scheme is the Compulsory Review of Exemptions and Audit Schemes, which is part of the International Maritime Organization's (IMO) efforts to improve maritime safety and environmental protection. The Voluntary IMO Member State Audit Scheme (VIMSAS) is a critical component of this audit scheme. VIMSAS aims to assess how effectively member states implement and enforce mandatory IMO instruments, such as the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS), the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL), and the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) (Maritime et al., 2018).

The audit scheme covers various aspects of maritime safety and environmental protection, including Mandatory instruments and national legislation, Areas of responsibility, Recognized organizations, Audit team selection, information on flag, coastal and port State activities, and Roles of critical stakeholders in shipping. The audit process involves sending questionnaires to maritime administrations to gather their perspectives on the scheme. The questionnaires cover misconceptions about the audit scheme, which is not well known outside the maritime industry. The audit results are available to member states, with feedback provided to assist in capacity-building and implementing applicable instruments. Lessons learned during the audits are also systematically fed back to IMO to improve the audit scheme. While the maritime industry has several audit schemes in place, there is a need for more legislative coherence and overarching policy direction to bind various ocean-based activities into a cohesive maritime aspiration (Garcia, 2023).

The participants were interviewed regarding the reason behind difficulties and their answers in the standardized assessments tool. Below are a few of their responses:

“Tas sa rule 38 ug sa audit scheme medyu naka limot nami ana.” (*And for rule 38 and the audit scheme, we have somewhat forgotten about this*). -RJM-

“Tapus sa rule 38 exemptions and audit scheme kay kana wala jud ko naka remember na, naay laboratory or simulator pero rarely lang” (*And for rule 38 and audit scheme, I could not remember this as we had laboratory or simulators only on rare occasions*). -RES-

“Ang rule 38 exemptions ug audit scheme kay naka limot na guro ko ana and wala ko naka study maong wala guro ko naka answer ana na mga topics sa survey ninyo” (*The rule 38 exemptions and audit scheme I think I have forgotten and I was not able to study which was why I was not able to answer correctly regarding those topics in your survey*). -BRJ-

Tapus sa rule 38 and kana audit scheme kay wala ko ana naka study gud mao guro wala ko naka answer” (*And with rule 38 and the audit scheme, I was not able to study which was why I could not answer correctly*). -MIMI-

“Tas ang sa rule 38 exemptions tas audit scheme kay naka limot ko ato while nag take sa survey ninyo kay wala ko naka review” (*And as for rule 38 exemptions and audit scheme, I have forgotten while taking your survey as I was not able to review*). -KYD-

“Tapus ang rule 38 ug kanang audit scheme kay wala ko naka remember sa kana na mga rules pag answer nako gud naka limot na guro” (*And for rule 38 and audit scheme, I could not remember those rules upon answering because I have forgotten it*). -DEBI-

Theme Cluster 3: Efficacy of Simulator and Hands-on Learning

The efficacy of simulators and hands-on learning in the maritime industry, particularly concerning COLREGs (International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea), is crucial to maritime education and training. Simulators play a significant role in enhancing training experiences by providing realistic scenarios and interactive learning environments. They offer increased fidelity and interaction experiences, aiding maritime trainees in acquiring technical and non-technical skills (Kim et al., 2021). Simulators, ranging from desktop-based to full-mission and virtual reality simulators, help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical experience, effectively preparing seafarers for real-world challenges. Using simulators in training and assessment enables seafarers to perform their duties safely and efficiently, combining individual and teamwork skills for better real-world application (VR Australian Maritime, 2022).

The integration of simulators in training and assessment aligns with the industry's technological advancements, such as ARPA, ECDIS, and AIS, providing essential practical training for smooth operation and compliance with maritime regulations like COLREGs. In conclusion, simulators and hands-on learning are integral components of maritime education and training, offering immersive experiences, enhancing skill acquisition, and ensuring seafarers' readiness for real-world challenges, including adhering to regulations like COLREGs (VR Australian Maritime, 2022).

The participants were interviewed regarding the reason behind difficulties and their answers in the standardized assessments tool. Below are a few of their responses:

“Sa sound signals sir medyu nag lisud ko ana kay sa una na topic kay wala gyud naka experience sa simulator kay mainly theory lang tas basa2 lang mi, maong mag lisud ko ana” (*With sound signals sir, I somewhat found those topics difficult since I was not able to experience it during simulators because it was mainly theory and reading, which was why I found it difficult*). -RES-

“ang sa sound signals sir kay nag lisud ko ana kay saamo na time rarely lang mag laboratory about ana puro lang kami basa2 ng lisud ko dum-dum ato na topic” (*With sound signals sir, I found it difficult because during our time we rarely were able to use the laboratory regarding those topics because we were only tasked to read which was why I could not remember that topic*). -MIMI-

Table 4 presented the mean or average scores and percentages and the mode, or most frequent scores and percentages among the data gathered. Along with this data, the corresponding interpretations were seen in the fourth column concerning how well the participants retained the lessons regarding COLREGS. It can be seen that the participants' average scores and percentages were 18.56 points and 37.12%, respectively. This indicated that the mean measure of central tendency was "very poor." As for the modal results among the data collected, the most frequent score and percentage observed were 21 points out of 50 correct answers and 42%, respectively. Similarly, this indicated that the modal measure of central tendency was "very poor" as well.

Table 5 tabulated the top 3 highest and lowest-performing participants according to the data gathered. Participant number 38 performed the best, scoring 37 out of 50, or 74% of the total score; this was interpreted as a "good" outcome. Following this score would be participants 19 and 21, with similar scores of 30 out of 50, or 60%. Although the result was a passing mark, this score would still be interpreted as "poor". Inversely, participant number 34 performed the worst among the 50 participants, resulting in only 8 out of 50 questions being answered correctly. Like most of the data gathered, this score showed a "very poor" interpretation as this participant only delivered with a percentage of 16%. The following two lowest-performing scores would be from participants 23 and 32, who scored 11 and 10 out of 50, or 22% and 20%, respectively.

Based on the responses after interviewing the participants, it was implied that more than memorization alone is needed to guarantee a high degree of learning retention regarding COLREGS. As stated, reviews regarding the topics involved and understanding key concepts and details regarding the rules in COLREGS were essential in attaining a high mark. More knowledge regarding COLREGS can be retained through frequent familiarization and constant reviews. Memorization is merely the foundation of understanding and knowledge retention. This must be accompanied by constant reviewing and understanding of the learned topic for optimal results. Reviewing is crucial and effective in supporting and reinforcing the memorized Information (Nasrollahi-Mouziraji & Nasrollahi-Mouziraji, 2015).

Table 6 presented the top 6 scoring participants who qualified the standardized assessment tool with a passing score of 50% and above. Presented on the table are the scores of each participant out of 50 points and the corresponding percentages after a simple percentage calculation. Along with these data were the interpretations based on the first table presented in the methodology portion of this academic paper.

Based on the data, it was to be implied that since only 6 out of 50 (12%) of the population retained information learned along the completion of this particular course, forgetting is exponential. This idea was supported by an article citing Hermann Ebbinghaus's research on the forgetting curve, which addressed that on average, fifty percent (50%) of what was learned was forgotten in 1 hour, seventy percent (70%) of this information was forgotten in a 24-hour day. Ninety percent (90%) of such information was lost after one week (Clearwater, 2022). According to the forgetting curve, the brain had a declining capability to store information. It was like the brain tends to forget certain information, especially when it was not reviewed frequently. It was seen that the rate of forgetting in the curve grew exponentially as days passed. Other curves exponentially grew slowly depending on several factors in learning retention. The forgetting rate depended on certain factors such as psychological factors like stress and day-to-day occurrences, how it was taught or presented, and how vital the information taught was to the individual (Shrestha, 2017).

Few students retained knowledge due to various factors such as the nature of memory, engagement levels, and the way information was processed. The implication was that while many people struggled with forgetting information and failing exams, there were individuals who successfully remembered and passed exams. By utilizing memory techniques such as organizing study materials, creating mind palaces, using mnemonics, and rhyming, individuals enhanced their ability to recall information effectively during exams. Focusing on critical details, understanding what instructors prioritize, and utilizing memory palaces further enhanced memory retention and exam success. Therefore, with dedication, practice, and the proper memory techniques, individuals overcame the challenge of forgetting and increased their chances of passing exams successfully (Oxford Royale, 2014).

Contributing Factors Leading to High and Low Scores

Throughout the learning process, factors always contribute to an individual's performance when it comes to academic performance and assessments. There are multiple factors as to why students have difficulties performing above a certain standard (Husaini & Shukor, 2023). Based on brief interviews with the participants, the researchers categorized the responses below based on generalized contributing factors.

Personality Traits. It posits that individuals have stable, enduring personality traits that influence their behavior and performance in various situations. In this context, certain personal traits such as motivation, resilience, and intelligence may contribute to achieving high and low scores (Diener & Lucas, 2015). Seafarers must treat the COLREGS with utmost importance. Failure to comply with these rules, essential for collision avoidance and safe navigation at sea, can lead to severe consequences,

including civil liability. Reports have shown that a significant percentage of incidents and collisions occur due to ignorance or violations of the COLREGS, highlighting the critical need for seafarers to understand and adhere to these regulations (The Editorial Team, 2019). COLREGS not only provides technical guidelines but also serves as legal norms for resolving ship collisions, emphasizing their vital role in ensuring maritime safety and preventing accidents at sea. Therefore, seafarers must maintain a proper lookout, follow the rules diligently, and exercise good seamanship to prevent collisions and ensure safe navigation (Seamanship Centre, 2019).

The participants have supported based on the brief interviews as to how their respective personality traits have affected their performance upon answering the standardized assessment tool.

“...unya wala sad ko ka review kay wala koy time” (*...and I was not able to review since I had no time.*). (Participant#32)

“...of course, ang colregs diman ma memorize permi akoo lang kay akoo lang gina pa familiarize ang mga important details sa rules tas review2 ginagmay” (*Of course, you cannot memorize COLREGS, I just familiarized the important details regarding the rules along with brief reviews.*) (Participant #38).

“Based sa pag answer nako sa questions, naka familiar lang ako sa uban and nahan pd ko sa COLREGS mag basa2.” (*Based on when I answered, I was familiar with some of the questions and I liked to read COLREGS*) (Participant #19).

“Nalingaw man sad ko ato answer2 gud...malingaw kog colregs kay importante kayna nga mabalan sa mga seaman” (*I had fun answering that time...I enjoy colregs because it is very important for a seaman to know*) (Participant #21).

Based on the participants' responses, an individual's outlook on a subject matter would affect one's performance and retention of knowledge. If one is willing to put time and effort into memorizing and reviewing the lessons learned, ideal retention will be achieved. Through the diligent conscientiousness of a student, one can attain exemplary results (Wang et al., 2023). Additionally, an implication can be derived and restated that mere memorization is insufficient when retaining information in the best way. As memorization is only the first fundamental principle, reviewing materials is best for better understanding and longer retention of lessons (Nasrollahi-Mouziraji & Nasrollahi-Mouziraji, 2015).

Surroundings. It can be challenging to concentrate on doing something outside. People are free to select whether or not they want to work inside or outside. One factor is the help of colleagues. For the benefit of people working outside, distractions like cell phones, the help of colleagues, public noise, and other endeavors that might have a harmful impact should also be eliminated. The reason why surroundings are a factor in high and low scores is due to the help of colleagues in answering the survey. One participant cannot focus on answering the survey due to distractions caused by the

colleagues' help. Another reason surroundings are a factor in high and low scores is noise. Noise can be a factor due to lack of concentration.

After a brief interview, a participant stated the following below which was categorized under surroundings.

“...tas naa akoo mego ato ni help sakoo tapad” (...my friend was there beside me to help) (Participant #21)

Based on this, an individual's surroundings, such as their peers in the immediate vicinity, can affect the assessment results. Although unideal in terms of assessments, it would be possible during the undergraduate time of these participants that such techniques were employed. It may be due to the lack of preparation and disregard for understanding and reviewing the assessed topics. However, it is safe to assume that cheating during assessments contributes to the betterment or detriment of the results (Diego, 2017).

Situations. An individual's situation often affects how well they can recall specific learned knowledge upon completing an assessment. Situational factors include time limitations and constraints and prior commitments throughout the day.

Upon a brief interview with the participants, the researchers categorized the responses which can only be described under situations.

“...nag dali dali ko ato ug answer nya wa nako sa focus... kay lage nag dali kos oras ato kay naa pami class and wala pud kaayo naka review.” (*I was in a rush to answer and I could not focus. I was limited by time since we still had classes to attend and I did not have the chance to review as much*) (Participant # 23)

“... naa koy gi apas gud napa koy lakaw ato paghuman nako training mao wa nako natarong pag answer sa survey...and wa nako nabasa ang mga questions ug ayo... gi paspasan lang nako ug answer ang survey” (*I was in a rush as I had somewhere to be after the trainings that was why I could not answer the survey properly. I did not read the questions thoroughly. I answered the survey hastily*) (Participant #32)

This implied that rushing an exam would likely lead to understood questions and complete considerations of items, leading to favorable results (Lu & Sireci, 2007). Although the participant's situation was understandable, as only a brief moment of their time was spared, the time constraint upon taking the assessment was undoubtedly a contributing factor. Reading through the questions thoroughly is essential to effectively apply the knowledge learned, as there is no need to rush assessments to achieve ideal results (Brubaker, 2022).

Conclusions

The study revealed that maritime transportation graduates retained little to no knowledge regarding COLREGS despite the critical applications it brings throughout their

career in seafaring. Within the given sample population, it can be inferred that further reviewing of sound signals, exemptions, and audit scheme rules must be conducted with the aid and implementation of simulator and hands-on training. Additionally, upon assessing retention levels, the individual's personality trait, surroundings, and situations must be considered. The crucial information regarding the rules of the road at sea learned within the classrooms was being overlooked and even forgotten. This may be a reflection on the learning system and methods when it comes to teaching COLREGS—furthermore, even the willingness of the students to learn.

Recommendations

The researchers proposed a program which illuminates the importance and refreshes the knowledge of COLREGS through refresher modules and reviewers. It addresses the poor learning retention of COLREGS by utilizing case studies, simulations, and assessments for maritime transportation students and graduates to restore the knowledge regarding collision regulations scenarios. This solution may be implemented within the academe setting as well as during the individual's vacant time in the form of modules, online mediums, realistic games and simulators, and even educational content on different platforms.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, several aspects with regards to ethics were considered to carefully address and ensure the integrity of this study as well as the welfare of the participants. Informed consent was the top priority considered to be obtained from the participants which informed them of the potential risks and benefits when agreeing to being a participant, as well as their right to withdraw from the study as they deemed fit without any repercussions. All pertinent data obtained were also kept strictly confidential as to preserve the anonymity and privacy of the participants. The researchers adhered to the ethical guidelines established by the institution and continuously ensured the compliance with ethical standards. To protect this study against plagiarism, the researchers adhered to the institution's policy of submitting a grammarly plagiarism check offered by the university's research office. The researchers merely interpreted the findings of the study based on the collected data to preserve the accuracy of the study's results.

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